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Numerical Analysis of Cross-Axis Wind Turbine for Different Pitch Angles

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ABSTRACT

A Cross-Axis Wind Turbine (CAWT) is a cross-axis blade configuration where six horizontal and three vertical blades are stacked in a cross-axis arrangement. Contrary to conventional horizontal axis wind turbines (HAWTs), a yaw mechanism is not required for it to operate. It also outperforms the standard vertical axis wind turbine (VAWT) by absorbing wind energy from all directions, making it flexible to variable wind conditions. The purpose of using a CAWT is to replace the traditional VAWT by generating more power. This study uses CAWT with different pitch angles to perform numerical analysis and determine the optimum one. All designs were assessed using ANSYS computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations, with the wind speed kept constant at 10 m/s and TSR variables adjusted to evaluate output. The blade design with a 5-degree pitch angle showed improved torque and power coefficients, according to simulation data.

KEYWORDS: CAWT (Cross Axis Wind Turbine), HAWT (Horizontal Axis Wind Turbine), VAWT (Vertical Axis Wind Turbine)

NOMENCLATURE

C_p	Coefficient of Power	C_t	Coefficient of Torque
D	Diameter of Rotor [m]	λ	Tip Speed Ratio

1. INTRODUCTION

Wind energy power has, recently grown to become one of the world's major utilizations of renewable energy in electricity generation and supply, displacing fossil energy sources [1]. Earlier types of wind energy came from wind turbines, particularly HAWT and VAWT. They have been of a great value in the emergence of renewable energy. But the fact is aggravated. As pressure rises to expand performance and, along with, the portion of innovation, it is possible to outline the shortcomings of such traditional designs. A new innovative wind energy technology that is under consideration at the moment is the wind turbine where the blades are in cross axis arrangements or the CAWT, which does not appear to fit in the horizontal or vertical axis categories of wind turbines.

The CAWT seeks to address some of the challenges associated with traditional designs, such as costs, the size of the land that is required, and maintenance requirements within the context of enhancements on efficiency, power tariffs, and versatility. The HAWT requires stable high wind velocity and large area for optimum performance. It employs forced yawing, which is accomplished by the use of the

turbine's yawing motion against the wind is maintained by electric motors and gearboxes [2]. It also needs substantial financial investment and leaves behind a significant carbon footprint during the production process [3]. The VAWT on the other hand is cheaper, easy to mass produce and more suitable for urban areas as compared to HAWT due to performing better in turbulent wind conditions [4]. But because of the vertical blade configuration, the VAWT can utilize less amount of wind leading to lower power production along with decreased efficiency [5]. The CAWT has embraced the features of the above two designs by relegating the lacking they possessed.

In the CAWT the area is increased where the wind interacts with the airfoils in order to capture wind energy more effectively from the approaching airflow. The vector of the vertical wind and horizontal blades can interact to provide lift by using the skewed airflow's vertical component. However, the unrealized energy coming from the normal flow which is perpendicular to the vertical blades can also be concurrently collected. The CAWT designs can harness horizontal and vertical wind planes, are more efficient, and generate more power. Therefore, by capturing the majority of the energy from the approaching wind, the airfoil-shaped framework can increase the turbine's ability to start on its own as well as improving the overall wind turbine performance. The CAWT's key benefit is that it has the ability to operate with omnidirectional flow of air coming along the horizontal direction towards the vertical blades and also coming through the horizontal blades from the bottom of the turbine creating a necessary lift force. Thus, increasing the power output, efficiency and coefficient of power of the turbine [6].

From an early study, it was concluded that in terms of power coefficient (C_p), the tip speed ratio, TSR and rotation per minute, the CAWT performed far better than the traditional 3-axis VAWT [7]. In another study the CAWT which was integrated in the top of a building showed for the minimum height above the rooftop of 100 mm the performance of CAWT increases significantly providing a greater performance from the CAWT [8]. A performance analysis experiment of the deflector integrated CAWT conducted by Chong et al concluded that a CAWT with a deflector included may generate 2.8 times more power than the VAWT [9]. A numerical study conducted by Chong et al and experimental result provided the data of the rotation per minute of a CAWT. The projected CAWT's maximum rotating speed of 609 rpm is 166% faster than the VAWT's highest rotational speed of 229 rpm [10]. Sivamani et al analyzed the turbine blades which were produced using thermoplastic materials ABS (Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene), made the blades highly weather resistant. It has been observed that the turbine's coefficient of power, C_p value steadily increases to its maximum value around the tip speed ratio, TSR= 1.20. The wind speed, $V = 10$ m/s results in the highest C_p value of 0.02385. Small wind turbines may therefore be made by utilizing the additive manufacturing and 3D printing technology

[11]. From another experiment, we can understand that, in order to acquire the optimum coefficient of power (C_p), the value of TSR (λ) must be 1 for the CAWTs 1.20; its wind speed is 10 m/s. It is also seen that the payback period for the CAWT was estimated to be 23 years based on its power output, which is considerably longer than that of the Savonius-type wind turbine. Consequently, the production cost is decreased and the CAWT's power output is increased [12]. However, none of these studies has adequately aimed at determining the optimal value of the pitch angle of CAWTs.

This study is an attempt to enhance the performance of CAWT in aerodynamics by determining the right combination of the NACA blade profiles and the right pitch angle. The relative performance of the CAWT can be examined using certain values, including torque and the power coefficient along with its different rotation per minute (RPM) values. With regard to the growth of global demand for energy sources and global environmental issues, the perspective of wind energy and, in particular, wind energy based on the CAWT concept can be utilized in a large scale. Considering recent advancements, the technology is projected to remain a critical factor in the reduction of greenhouse emissions, enhancing energy security, and as part of a reliable and clean energy solution.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

2.1 Design

The outcome of this research is the design and creation of an innovative Cross-Axis Wind Turbine (CAWT), for which the goal is to deliver optimum performance with regard to several parameters. The CAWT design comprises of three vertically orientated blades, along with six blades placed in horizontal direction. The blade profiles essential for aerodynamic efficiency were selected from the NACA 4-series aerofoils, with the NACA0018 profile chosen due to its symmetrical shape. The symmetrical design is ideal for two-directional airflow along with having strong body integrity. The parameters used to design the models are provided in table 1

Table 1. Parameters for different parts of CAWT Wind Turbine

Diameter of the Rotor	35 cm
Horizontal Blades	
Chord length, C	3.4 cm
Length, L	15 cm
Number of Blades	6
Vertical Blades	
Chord length, C	5 cm
Length, L	30 cm
Number of Blades	3

Figure 1. Final Model of Cross-Axis

These were incorporated using a SolidWorks model as a means of ensuring precision in the blade and the complete turbine construction. The connectors were provided deliberately to effectively interconnect the

vertical and horizontal blades and give them the right stance. An angle of 60 degrees were kept between upper and lower horizontal blades while mounting them to the hub. Also, the connecting hub, which secures the horizontal blades to the circular shaft, was made to transmit the power received from the blades to the shaft effectively in order to accommodate alterations to the pitch angles. Therefore, the CAWT design provides a strong frame with well-shaped blades and pitches to embrace the wind from any angle as shown in Figure 1. Significant factors in converting wind energy using a CAWT include using NACA airfoil profiles, precise construction of the connector form, and ensuring the blade angle is correct, making it suitable for different wind conditions.

2.2 Numerical Setup and Simulation

The design of the CAWT was further optimized from the original design by using computational fluid dynamics (CFD) by comparing its performance between the different conditions. This numerical analysis was made possible using ANSYS fluent. The rotating domain having a parameter of 1.5D where ‘D’ represents the diameter of the rotor which rotates at varying TSRs throughout the investigation. The dimensions of the fixed domain is used as 14D x 8D x 10D respectively. The sliding mesh mechanism is used because of unstable flow in the region where tetrahedron unstructured mesh is generated having 176225 nodes and 817508 elements shown in the Figure 2. The CFD simulation was performed using a pressure-based, transient, planar solver configuration within the fluent setup. The $k-\omega$ SST turbulence model was chosen as the viscous model because of its strong performance and wide applicability in similar scenarios [13]. This model was preferred for its ability to more accurately differentiate and predict boundary layer flows with greater precision. With 10 m/s of inlet velocity the models were tested. In the Figure 3 the pressurized regions are represented following the numerical analysis. It is observable that the leading edges of the blades and connectors are the most susceptible regions to force. The rest of the turbine produce smooth output in any applied wind condition.

Figure 2. Fixed Domain and Rotating Domain Mesh Outlook

Figure 3. Pressure Point represented through CFD simulation

3. RESULT

This research has discussed the effects of the moderate geometry of blades and their rates on the turbine and affected all of these points to get the appropriate rate of efficiency, torque, and rotation per minute (RPM). The findings shown below indicate that the model with 5 degree pitch angle outperforms other modified NACA models different pitch angles. While evaluating the impact of pitch angles on turbine performance, the model with a pitch angle of 5 degrees performs better with a TSR (λ) of 0.8 or higher. This model produces a greater power coefficient (C_p) and torque coefficient (C_t) than the general model with a 0 degree pitch angle. The models with 10 and 15 degree pitch angles are inferior to what this model produces. But based on the results observed in terms of the rotational speed, the base model, achieves the maximum RPM of 265.8. This rate is much higher than the other models, especially in contrast to the 5 degree pitch angle model, which is behind. In terms of rotation per minute (RPM), the base model outperformed the nearest 5 degree model by 4.97 percent.

Fig. 4. Power and Torque Coefficient vs Different Pitch Angle

Fig. 5. Rotation per Minute vs Different Pitch Angles

The C_p of the turbine, which is an indication of the efficiency of the turbine, is higher in the 5 degree pitch angle model than in the base model. When calculating the power coefficient (C_p), the 5 degree model brings an improvement of 5.53 percent compared to the 0-degree base model. However, this improvement is only when the TSR (λ) is higher than 0.8, as is evident from Fig.4 .When the level of TSR (λ) is comparatively low, the base model reinforces its advantage. When analyzing the velocity contours, it is observed that the base model yields less wake than the 5 degree blade model. This may mean that, so far as practical applications are concerned, the base model is a better option, especially when generating a moderate wake while working on low air speed environments.

Fig. 6. Power Coefficient of Different Pitch Angles with varying TSR

Finally, the work emphasizes the importance of the 5-degree pitch angle to maximize the turbine efficiency for the higher tip speed ratios. As such, these insights can be invaluable when undertaking research aimed at tailoring the turbine design to different operating conditions or developing better designs that help guarantee the reliable performance of energy systems.

4. CONCLUSION

To conclude, this research demonstrates that cross-axis wind turbines (CAWT) can be used as an alternative source of power generation for green and sustainable energy in countries like Bangladesh, where wind speed is very low. The experiment with the different blade pitch angles showed that a blade inclination of 5 degrees was favorable in high-speed winds, which improved the turbine's coefficient of torque and power. Alternatively, the base model design outperformed other designs, making it more suitable for operating in wind speed which are significantly lower than average wind condition in environment. Through these findings, it is validated that for different wind conditions, the CAWT can be effectively operated by changing the blade pitch angle, thus making it financially and spatially efficient in contrast to horizontal-axis wind turbines. In future, it is possible to reduce the cost of the designs by testing it further to accommodate a broader application, and applying these designs on a larger scale could feasibly help make the production of energy a more sustainable process.

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